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Interfacial properties of MXene/graphene/polymer matrix nanocomposites

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Introduction

- Graphene (GP) as the most popular material due to its excellent electric, mechanical properties. However, GP has hydrophobic surface resulting insufficient mechanical reinforcement effect.
- MXene has uncommon combination of metallic conductivity and hydrophilicity. Hydrophilicity could determine the strong interface interaction between MXene and polymer matrix. In order to utilize the advantages of MXene in MXene/GP/polymer matrix nanocomposites, a comprehensive understanding of MXene surface properties is crucial.
- **The aim of this study** is to determine the interfacial adhesion and compatibility at MXene-polymer matrix interface and the overall composite performance.

Methods

Representative volume elements of MXene/GP/epoxy matrix nanocomposites

Study of MXene and epoxy interfacial strength by contact angle measurements

The work of adhesion describes the energy required during fracture of a filler–matrix interface:

$$W_{s_1s_2} = \gamma_{s_1} + \gamma_{s_2} - \gamma_{s_1s_2}$$

γ_{s_1} is the surface tension of the MXene

γ_{s_2} is the surface tension of epoxy

$\gamma_{s_1s_2}$ is interfacial tension

MXene-epoxy matrix interfacial strength

- MXene exhibits a high surface energy ($\gamma_s = 52.1 - 72.5 \text{ mJ/m}^2$) and is able to **form strong adhesive bonds** with polymer matrix.
- The **interfacial strength** predicted by the thermodynamic work of adhesion at the MXene-epoxy interface was found to be **$W = 130.5 \text{ mJ/m}^2$** .

Mechanical behaviour of MXene/GP/epoxy nanocomposite

- Addition of 2.5 vol.% of MXenes in the GP/epoxy composition increases modulus, but decreases strength of nanocomposite independently on the interaction at GP and epoxy matrix interface.

Stress–strain curves for MXene/GP/epoxy nanocomposites at different strength at GP and epoxy interface

Mechanical behaviour of MXene/GP/epoxy nanocomposite

- The higher volume fraction of MXenes (10 vol. %) significantly increases Young modulus and strength of the MXene/GP/epoxy matrix nanocomposite.

Stress–strain curves for MXene/GP/epoxy nanocomposites at different MXene content

